

TABLE 1

Metal ion	$R_f^a \times 100$						Detection limit (in% w/v)	Colour of the spots
	Plain Silica gel		Impregnated layers					
	Solvent A	Solvent B	Solvent A		Solvent B			
Reference			Mixture	Reference	Mixture			
Group I								
Co(II) (Nitrate)	0	0	53	53	58	58	0.025	Violet
Zn (Acetate)	03	05	81	84	87	87	0.025	Dark pink
Cr (Chloride)	0	0	18	18	23	22	0.075	Green
Ni(II) (Sulphate)	0	0	49	48	52	51	0.075	Green
Al (Chloride)	—	—	31	31	34	34	0.075	Pinkish yellow
Cu(II) (Sulphate)	05	12	80	80	83	83	0.05	Chocolate
Sn(IV) (Chloride)	0	0	62	61	64	63	0.05	Yellowish orange
Fe(II) (Sulphate)	07T	08T	70	70	72	72	0.025	Light blue
Group II								
As(III) (Oxide)	16T	26T	29	29	31	31	0.05	Light yellow
Pb(II) (Acetate)	0	0	60	60	64	64	0.05	Yellow
Sb (Chloride)	30T	32T	56	55	61	60	0.05	Orange
Hg(IV) (Chloride)	14	26	95	95	95	95	0.025	Yellow
Cd (Nitrate)	0	0	73	73	78	78	0.05	Yellowish orange
Ag (Nitrate)	0	0	51	50	53	52	0.05	Black
Se (Dioxide)	44T	45T	65	65	69	69	0.025	Yellow

a = The values are average of two identical runs.
 (-) = not visualised.
 T = Tailing.

Experimental

Preparation of Ceric Molybdate : Ceric molybdate was prepared by mixing ammonium molybdate (0.05M) and ceric ammonium nitrate (0.05M) at room temperature ($30 \pm 2^\circ$). The initial pH of the ceric solution was adjusted with sulphuric acid. The precipitate in contact with liquid was left overnight at room temperature. It was then filtered, washed first with dilute sulphuric acid and then with deionised water and dried.

The TLC plates (thickness 0.5 mm) were prepared by spreading a slurry of a mixture of 50 g of silica gel G and 1.0 g of ceric molybdate (200 mesh) in 100 ml of distilled water and drying for 24 hrs at a constant temperature of 45° .

The inorganic ions (0.1% w/v solution in water) were applied to the layers using glass capillary and the chromatograms were eluted at constant temperature ($30 \pm 1^\circ$) with a mixture of benzene-ethyl acetate-acetic acid-HCl (60 : 30 : 10 : 0.5) solvent A or (60 : 30 : 10 : 1.0) solvent B. After development the plates were sprayed with 0.5% dithiazone in chloroform. Results are shown in Table 1. For comparison sake, the chromatographic behaviour of these metal ions on plain silica gel is also given. It may be noted that on plain silica gel a streak of HCl (used in solvent system) is formed a little above the base line which hinders the movement of most of the metal ions and thus prevents their separation.

It is found that a satisfactory separation is obtained on impregnated plate if the ions are

divided into two groups. Further it is seen that for ions of Group I, solvent B is a better solvent system while for ions of Group II, solvent A is more suitable. It is significant to observe that the R_f value does not alter appreciably when the ions are present in mixture. As expected the R_f value in solvent B, which is more polar, are greater than those in solvent A.

Reference

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Physico-chemical Studies on Weak Charge-transfer Complexes. I. Complexation of Phthalic Anhydride with Naphthalene

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THE unsaturated anhydrides¹⁻³ such as maleic and some substituted maleic anhydrides (MA and S-MA), tetrahalophthalic anhydrides, pyromellitic dianhydride (PMDA), trimellitic anhydride, etc., are known, to form molecular complexes with π - and n -electron donors. The unsubstituted phthalic

anhydride (PA) has been very little investigated with regard to its ability to form molecular addition compounds. The charge-transfer π - π interaction between phthalic anhydride, a π -electron acceptor, and a series of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons acting as π -donors was studied by Choudhury¹⁰ who determined only the CT-absorption maxima of the complexes but not their physico-chemical properties in solution.

We have, therefore, undertaken a systematic investigation of molecular complexes formed between PA and several aromatic π - and n -donors in the solvent chloroform by spectrophotometric methods with the object of determining (a) equilibrium constant (K), (b) molar absorptivity (ϵ_c), (c) relative and absolute compositions and (d) dependence, if any, of the equilibrium constant on wavelength, etc.

As a part of our programme we report in this short communication the results of our investigations on Naphthalene-PA complex.

Experimental

PA and naphthalene were purified by repeated sublimation, their m.p.'s were checked to be 130 and 81° respectively. Chloroform (E. Merck) was double distilled just before use. Stock solutions of the acceptor and donor in chloroform were prepared by direct weighing and from these, the solutions used in the final measurements were obtained by appropriate dilution.

All absorption measurements were made in well-matched 4 cm quartz cells in Hilger UVISPEK Spectrophotometer using the solvent blank as reference in all cases except in the determination of CT-absorption maxima of PA-naphthalene complex where the donor blank was used as the reference. The experiments were carried out at room temperatures which were normally within 27-29°.

Results and Discussion

The CT-band of PA-naphthalene complex, located at 327 nm, is broad and structureless. Since the acceptor and the donor absorb strongly in the region of CT-absorption maxima, accurate determination of K values at the CT-peak is not possible. Therefore, the CT-interaction between naphthalene and PA has been studied at wavelengths well removed from the absorption peak. At the shifted wavelengths the absorption due to the complex is appreciable but that due to the acceptor and the donor is small but not negligible. The small absorption still shown by the acceptor and the donor has been corrected for during calculation of physico-chemical parameters of the complex in solution. Accordingly, we have chosen by trials four wavelengths in the range 345 to 358 nm for the

study of the PA-naphthalene complex. The relative composition of the complex determined at each of the following four wavelengths, viz., 345, 350, 355 and 358 nm respectively by Job's method of Continuous Variation¹¹, has been found to be 1 : 1. The absolute composition of a complex having the general formula A_mD_n , i.e., the actual values of m and n , m and n being respectively the mole numbers of the acceptor (A) and the donor (D) in which the combination has taken place, is determined with the help of the following equation¹²

$$\log D = (m+n) \log {}_iC_A + \text{constant} \quad \dots (1)$$

where $D = d_{\text{obs}} - d_A^\circ - d_D^\circ = \epsilon {}_iC_C$, the constant is equal to $(n/m)^n K \epsilon$ and $\epsilon = \epsilon_c - m\epsilon_A - n\epsilon_D$.

The equation (1) has been derived by combining suitably the following equations (2), (3) and (4) and approximating that the complex is weak and ${}_iC_A$ is small.

In Job's method of continuous variation at a fixed value of ${}_iC_A + {}_iC_D$ but with varying ${}_iC_A : {}_iC_D$ ratios, the maximum optical density is observed at

$$\frac{{}_iC_A}{{}_iC_D} = \frac{m}{n} \quad \dots (2)$$

(the ratio m/n determines the relative composition of the complex).

The equilibrium constant of the complex (for the general reaction $mA + nD \rightleftharpoons A_mD_n$) is given by

$$K = \frac{C_c}{({}_iC_A - mC_c)^m ({}_iC_D - nC_c)^n} \quad \dots (3)$$

The equation (3) in conjunction with equation (2) reduces to the following approximate form

$$C_c = (n/m)^n K {}_iC_A^{m+n} \quad \dots (4)$$

when the complex is weak. For the PA-Naphthalene complex studied in the present investigation linear plots (not shown) of $\log D$ vs $\log {}_iC_A$ as demanded by the equation (1) have been obtained at all the four wavelengths. A separate experiment on Job's method of Continuous Variation establishes that for the complex under study m/n is unity. Thus both m/n and $m+n$ being known, m and n are separately evaluated. The results are shown in the last column of the Table 1 which shows that the mole numbers of the acceptor and the donor are strictly unity. Experiments under conditions from equimolar to excess of either component have been carried out to evaluate K and ϵ_c values at the mentioned wavelengths by utilising different equations¹³⁻¹⁶ currently in use for the purpose. The results are shown in Table 1. As required for (1 : 1) complex formation the data on graphical analysis according to equations¹³⁻¹⁶ confirmed well to straight line plots. The values of K and ϵ_c

TABLE 1

λ(nm)	Equimolar condition									Varying concentrations of donor with fixed concentration of acceptor						Average	Relative composition m : n	Absolute Composition Individual values of m and n	
	Foster equation ^{1a}			Modified Ketelaar equation ¹⁴			Rose-Drago equation ¹⁶			B-H equation ¹³			Modified Ketelaar ¹⁴						
	K	ε _c	Kε _c	K	ε _c	Kε _c	K	ε _c	Kε _c	K	ε _c	Kε _c	K	ε _c	Kε _c				K
345	0.61	123	75.0	0.65	115	74.8	0.68	111	75.5	0.68	113	76.8	0.68	114	77.5	0.66	115	1 : 1	m=1 ; n=1
350	0.79	75	59.3	0.75	79	59.3	0.77	76	58.5	0.65	91	59.2	0.65	92	59.8	0.72	83	1 : 1	m=1 ; n=1
355 ₁	1.38	34	46.9	1.39	34	47.3	1.40	32	47.7	1.34	35	46.9	1.33	37	49.2	1.39	34	1 : 1	m=0.96 ; n=0.96
358	1.56	25	39.0	1.51	26	39.3	1.63	24	39.1	1.82	23	41.9	1.82	23	41.9	1.67	24	1 : 1	m=1 ; n=1

$$\text{Foster equation } \frac{iC_A l}{(d-d_A-d_D)} = \frac{1}{K(\epsilon_C - \epsilon_A - \epsilon_D)iC_A} + \frac{2}{(\epsilon_C - \epsilon_A - \epsilon_D)}$$

$$\text{B-H equation } \frac{iC_A l}{(d-d_A-d_D)} = \frac{1}{(\epsilon_C - \epsilon_A - \epsilon_D)} + \frac{1}{K(\epsilon_C - \epsilon_A - \epsilon_D)iC_D}$$

$$\text{Modified Ketelaar equation } \frac{iC_A iC_D l}{(d-d_A-d_D)(C_A + iC_D)} = \frac{1}{K(\epsilon_C - \epsilon_A - \epsilon_D)(iC_A + iC_D)} + \frac{1}{(\epsilon_C - \epsilon_A - \epsilon_D)}$$

$$\text{Rose-Drago equation } \frac{iC_A iC_D l}{(d-d_A-d_D)} = \frac{1}{K(\epsilon_C - \epsilon_A - \epsilon_D)} + \frac{(iC_A + iC_D)}{(\epsilon_C - \epsilon_A - \epsilon_D)} - \frac{(d-d_A-d_D)}{(\epsilon_C - \epsilon_A - \epsilon_D)^2}$$

iC_A = initial concentration of the acceptor, iC_D = initial concentration of the donor,
 d = optical density of the solution, d_A = optical density of the acceptor,
 d_D = optical density of the donor, ϵ_C = molar extinction coefficient of the complex,
 ϵ_A = molar extinction coefficient of the acceptor, ϵ_D = molar extinction coefficient of the donor.

determined graphically are in close agreement with least-square results shown in Table 1 which shows several important features about PA-Naphthalene complex. We notice that K increases while ε_c decreases with increase in wavelength. These observations are true under widely varying experimental conditions from equimolar to excess concentration of either components in solution.

The absorption maxima of TCPA*-Naphthalene and of PA-Naphthalene complexes are 354 and 327 nm respectively. The molar absorbance of PA-Naphthalene complex at 355 nm is approximately 34, while that of TCPA-Naphthalene complex is 1000 at 354 nm, which is considerably higher than that of PA-Naphthalene complex. The molar extinction coefficients of the complex at the other wavelengths studied are much lower than that of TCPA-Naphthalene complex. The K-values of PA-Naphthalene complex at all the four wavelengths are lower than that (2.8 l mole⁻¹ at 354 nm) of TCPA-Naphthalene complex. All the above results suggest that PA is a weak electron acceptor than TCPA. The low extinction coefficient of PA-Naphthalene complex suggests the absence of Mulliken-Orgel¹⁷ type of contact charge transfer complex. The K-values vary

systematically with wavelength (λ), increasing with increase in λ. Similar observations have been made by other workers¹⁸⁻²⁰ in connection with the studies of other types of molecular complexes. Three reasons, e.g., (i) existence of higher order complexes, (ii) deviations from Beer's law, (iii) solvent perturbation are generally advanced to account for the observed variation of K with λ. The change of K under equimolar concentrations of both the components, a condition where the formation of (1 : 1) type of complex is more favourable than other types, suggests that the factor (i) is not strictly valid in the present case. Perhaps the last two causes play the more important roles, particularly the solvent perturbation effect since chloroform is not as inert as it was thought to be. NMR studies²¹⁻²³ offer direct support for interaction between chloroform and the aromatic π-electron system acting as a base.

Variations in the values of K and ε_c obtained by equimolar and non-equimolar methods are noted in the present study. Such variations in K and ε_c according to the condition [D] >> [A] (where [] denotes concentration) have been observed by many workers^{18, 23, 24}, although the product Kε_c remains fairly constant²⁵.

* Tetrachlorophthalic Anhydride

There are divergent opinions regarding the observed differences in K and ϵ_c , the current view, held by most investigators^{2,4}, is the deviation from Beer's law by the complex. Assuming that ϵ_c varies as some function of the concentration of the excess component, usually the donor, Foster et al^{2,4} has shown that a small difference in the extinction coefficient of a complex in a pure solvent and in the same solvent but containing sufficient concentrations of D (or A) can account for the observed differences in the calculated values of K and ϵ_c , although the product $K\epsilon_c$ is constant. The same authors (loc.cit) have shown that minimum deviation from Beer's law for a given measurable concentration of 1:1 complex would occur only when the total solute concentration is minimum, i.e., under the condition $[D]=[A]$. According to Person^{2,6} a better value of the formation constant can be obtained when the concentration of the complex is of the same order of magnitude as that of the most dilute component. It can be shown by simple calculation that keeping the total solute concentration a minimum a larger concentration of the complex with 1:1 stoichiometry can be obtained under equimolar condition than under non-equimolar situation. All these can, therefore, explain the observed differences in the values of K and ϵ_c obtained by equi- and non-equimolar methods. The product $K\epsilon_c$, however, shows a fair constancy in the magnitudes at any particular wavelength, as shown in Table I.

Work on molecular complex formation reaction between PA and a series of substituted benzenes and several condensed benzenes is in progress.

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Ag(I), Pb(II) and Zn(II) Complexes of Penicillin-V

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IN continuation of the studies from these laboratories on the chelation reactions of Penicillins¹⁻³ the present communication reports the study of Ag(I), Pb(II) and Zn(II) complexes of Penicillin-V.

Experimental and Results

All the reagents employed were of high purity. The preparation and standardisation of the metal and the ligand solutions and other experimental details remaining the same as given in the earlier communication³.

Stoichiometry of the complexes formed was ascertained by potentiometric (pH) and conductometric studies. The Bjerrum-Calvin⁴ pH-titration technique as adopted by Irving-Rossotti⁵ was followed to determine various formation constants. For

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